

STUDY OF THE PROCESSES OF MERCHANDISING AND REMOTE PURCHASES IN THE ANDROID ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation: The article covers significant information about the processes of merchandising. Moreover, in the article general concepts of merchandising and main tasks of merchandisers were highlighted.

Key words: *buying and selling, advertising, display, target customers, ambience, harmonious reception, store-house.*

In the present context, Merchandising has evolved into a more specialized field. In the days of Mom & Pop store, the owner of the store was doing the job of complete management of the store including that of the merchandiser. Over a period of time the formats of stores have gone into complete change, including the size, ambience, type of merchandise stored, specialization in merchandise sales, use of technology in managing sales and stocks, and job specializations. The merchandising as a concept and process has gone into a complete sea change. Merchandising means the buying and selling of goods with a motive to earn profit. The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines the word 'merchandise' as goods bought and sold or trade goods. According to Business Dictionary, 'merchandise' refers to goods and commodities sold at the retail level. Merchandising focuses on the buying, presenting, and selling of merchandise. This includes all related activities such as advertising, display, and promotion of merchandise involving the retail customers.

According to American Marketing Association, merchandising is the planning involved in marketing the right merchandise at the right place at the right

time in the right quantities at the right price. To this definition, we can further add “marketing to the right target customers[1].” This addition may give a completeness to the merchandising process. Many Retailers would vouch for achieving the perfect balance among the right merchandise, right place, right time, right quantity, and right price as a great challenge. Retailers who can achieve them are surely successful in their venture. Grace Kunz has tried to capture the essence of merchandizing when he defines merchandising as the planning, developing, and presenting of product lines for identified target markets with regard to pricing, assorting, styling, and timing. Nora Aufreiter et al. have tried summarizing the concept of merchandising very succinctly as follows: ‘Merchandising is not a synonym for the buying function, it is an integrated, end-to-end business process that runs from planning the assortment, to sourcing, to distribution, to allocation of the goods to the stores, to promoting and selling the assortment to the customers and finally to replenishing inventory as necessary. The other activities that make merchandising effective, such as advertising, displaying, creating an attractive ambience, harmonious reception of the visitors i.e. prospective customers. In fact, Merchandising is the art of marketing the right merchandise at the right place at the right time in the right quantity at the right price. The success of the merchandising lies in these five ‘Rights’. In the absence of these five rights, the retailer cannot be successful in his endeavor. Different authors have emphasized different points in the context of merchandising. For example, Grace Kunz has emphasized on the planning, developing and presenting of the product lines to the target markets with regard to the styling, assorting, timing and pricing. Lewison on the other hand has advocated that merchandising is the process of developing, obtaining, pricing supporting and communicating the retailer’s merchandise offering.

The process of merchandising involves understanding consumer needs, identifying & sourcing of right merchandise, deciding the right assortment, planning distribution of merchandise to different locations in the right quantities, deciding on the pricing, communicating merchandise offerings to the target

customers, and taking feedback of consumers[2]. The role of merchandiser has gone into tremendous transformation from the historical time. Traditionally, merchandisers were really performing more a role of a merchant selling different kinds of merchandise to different towns and villages in the same country or in another country

The role of merchandisers in later period underwent the above change mainly due to his association with the export business. In historical times, the merchandiser himself was travelling to different countries to sell his merchandise. In the later period, the merchandiser's role became more specialized and he was assisting the businessman or the Firm. The Firms were selling goods to different countries as part of the export business. This activity is more of a business to business contact. The new roles of merchandiser in an exporting organization are as follows: The First Contact Person: He/she is the first contact person in an organization with whom the buyer (the buyer as a representative of the buying organization from another country) comes in contact after the top level contact has been established. He/she is also the first person in any manufacturing/ marketing organization with whom the merchandiser/buyer from the buying organization gets in touch for making preliminary enquiries. Store house of Information: He/she is expected to be a store-house of all the information that will help him/her to provide quick and prompt details during the meetings with the buyers. Customer's Friend/Advisor: Merchandiser should also be able to suggest a suitable quality to the buyer based on his requirement. For example, if the buyer enquires that he is looking for a medium weight quality in Knitted T-Shirt Garment, say for a summer season[3].

The merchandiser should be in a position to suggest to the buyer a suitable quality say in single jersey or pique or any other suitable knit fabric in 200/250 GSM or something similar or suitable. Merchandiser should have good knowledge about his buyers' requirements, particularly about the buyers who are the regular ones. This helps him to make new and varied offerings to his buyers during the

buying season. Boss' Man-Friday: Merchandiser is the owner's or boss' confidante and a Man Friday in many different ways. He/she is like an errand runner and must supply the boss with many varied kind of materials. For example, in case of garment export - right from fabric cuttings/samples, accessories, garment samples to costing information should be provided immediately[4]. Many a times he must arrange for samples and make other arrangements at the last moment in an unexpected meeting with an unexpected buyer. Production/ Order co-ordinator: The merchandiser must constantly remain in touch with the production unit to keep himself/herself updated with latest position on the production front. He/she must keep the production unit constantly updated with buyer's requirements. In fact, right from the point of receipt of an order till its dispatch, the merchandiser must be aware of every move or action on this front.

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